

Operational Use of SSM/I Ice Concentration in the Initialization of a Coupled Ice-Ocean Model

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INTRODUCTION

The Polar Ice Prediction System (PIPS), the Regional Polar Ice Prediction System – Barents (RPIPS-B) and the Regional Polar Ice Prediction System – Greenland Sea (RPIPS-G) are all operational sea ice forecasting systems which have been run daily at the Fleet Numerical Meteorology and Oceanography Center (FNMOC) since September 1987, June 1989 and October 1991, respectively. The basis for all three models is the Hibler ice model (Hibler, 1979; 1980). The Hibler ice model calculates ice drift, ice thickness, ice concentration (ice edge) and the growth/decay of ice based on both dynamic and thermodynamic effects. The Polar Ice Prediction System 2.0 (PIPS2.0), a new version of PIPS, is presently undergoing its final test phase. PIPS2.0 has been modified into a spherical coordinate version of PIPS and coupled with an ocean model (Cox, 1984). Daily atmospheric fields from the Navy Operational Global Atmospheric Prediction System (NOGAPS) (Rosmond, 1981; Hogan et al., 1990) are used to produce a 24-hour forecast.

PIPS forecasts over the entire Arctic basin, the Barents Sea and the Greenland/Norwegian Sea using a grid resolution of 127 km. RPIPS-B, a higher resolution version of PIPS, forecasts over the Barents Sea and the western part of the Kara Sea using a grid resolution of 25 km. RPIPS-G, another higher resolution version of PIPS, forecasts over the region adjacent to the East Greenland coast using a grid resolution of 20 km. PIPS2.0 forecasts over most of the ice-covered regions in the northern hemisphere using a variable grid resolution ranging from 17 to 33 km at the North Pole (Fig. 1). By the end of 1994, PIPS2.0 will replace all the

existing operational forecast systems at FNMOC. The time step used by all four ice models is 6 hours. Each model is restarted daily using its own 24-hour forecast. Once per week, each of the operational system's ice concentration field is initialized (updated) by the digitized analysis of ice concentration from the Navy/NOAA National Ice Center (NIC) [formerly the Joint Ice Center (JIC)]. A detailed description of PIPS may be found in Preller and Posey (1989). A detailed description of RPIPS-B may be found in Preller et al. (1989). A preliminary study of RPIPS-G may be found in Preller et al. (1990). Unlike the operational models, PIPS2.0 was run daily on a Cray-YMP located at Stennis Space Center. This model is not run operationally, which means that no initialization (updating) of the ice concentration occurs. A 24-hour simulation was performed daily using the real time NOGAPS forcing. A more detailed description of the ice-ocean model may be found in Cheng and Preller (1992).

Ice concentration data from the Defense Meteorological Satellite Program (DMSP) Special Sensor Microwave Imager (SSM/I) have been interpolated to the ice model grids of the Navy's Polar Ice Prediction Systems with the intention of using these concentrations for regular updating of the ice models. Although the NIC's ice concentration analysis is generated on Wednesday, the information is not usually ready for use by PIPS until Friday, resulting in an update that is 2 days old. The optimal situation would be to have initialization data available daily, as opposed to weekly. SSM/I ice concentration data provides this capability. In this paper, SSM/I data will be presented and discussed in terms of its usefulness as an initialization field for PIPS2.0. Results from a number of forecasts, with and without the SSM/I initialization, will be compared to each other and to other available data in order to determine the degree of improvement that the SSM/I can lend to the existing operational system.

DATA

The Naval Research Laboratory (NRL) has been collecting and archiving SSM/I ice concentration data since May 1991 (Lundeen et al., 1993). Ice concentration values are derived from SSM/I brightness temperatures by applying the U.S. Navy's ice concentration algorithm. This algorithm is a streamlined version of the AES/York algorithm as described in Hollinger (1991). NRL collects the data from FNMOC's Environmental Data Repository via an automated data program that retrieves the data from satellite swaths at approximately 25 km resolution. Initially the coverage retrieved by NRL was only large enough to cover the PIPS domain, extending from the Pole down to approximately 60° N. In March 1993, coverage was expanded down to 40° N to gain a more complete coverage of the ice forming in the marginal seas, including the Sea of Okhotsk, Hudson Bay, the Labrador Sea and the Gulf of St. Lawrence. In October 1993, the coverage was extended to 20° N to include coverage of ice forming in the Yellow Sea region. NRL accesses these data files twice per day. The two files together provide sufficient coverage of the Arctic polar region as well as the marginal seas.

Figure 1.

PIPS2.0 domain with regional models included (PIPS, RPIPS-B and RPIPS-G).

DATA PROBLEMS

Interpolating the SSM/I data presented several problems most of which were correctable. It was noted that some of the ice concentration values were indeterminate and some values read greater than 100% concentration. The indeterminate values were removed without any significant loss of coverage due to the large amount of data available. The ice concentrations greater than 100% were reduced to 100%. Another problem was the data void region from 88–90° N resulting from the orbit of the satellite. For this region, 100% ice concentration is assumed during interpolation.

Even though two data files provide sufficient coverage for one day, gaps could occur in information due to a variety of causes such as transmission loss, program failure, truncation of the data file and failure in the data link between FNMOC and NRL. To make SSM/I data useful in regularly updating the ice models, gaps in the data are replaced with the previous day's data. Substitution occurs when zero ice concentration is found at a data point that had 50% ice concentration the previous day. The previous day's values then replace the zero values of the current day. This ensures a smooth continuous ice field from one day to the next.

Another problem occurs when spurious ice concentration values are formed in areas where no ice should exist. These values often appear in one of the following forms. As the satellite transitions from land to water, small or low concentrations along the shore may occur. Most of this problem is corrected by converting all ice concentrations below 20% equivalent to zero. The data are adjusted in this way for use in the numerical models. Values less than 15% are treated as open water by the models. Small arcs of concentration occur mainly in the Greenland and Labrador Seas and occasionally in the Sea of Okhotsk. These arcs are easily distinguishable from the real ice concentrations and their occurrence may be related to passing storms. Another problem occurs in the regions between 40° and 60° N in the Sea of Japan, the Pacific Ocean and the Grand Banks area of the Atlantic Ocean during the summer months from May through the beginning of October. The reason for these erroneous values is unknown at this time but may be due to the treatment of cloud cover and storms in the ice concentration algorithm.

To adjust for small gaps in the ice concentration data resulting from slight differences between the SSM/I algorithm land boundaries and the ice model land boundaries, a correction routine was added to fill in these gaps with ice concentrations from surrounding grid points. These corrections were to insure the compatibility of the ice model and the SSM/I data in the model initialization process.

There is another possible solution that can be used to correct the problems mentioned above. The algorithm applied to the brightness temperatures could be reviewed and corrected. However, this may take a substantial amount of time and we hope to use this data in an automated operational fashion within the coming year. As an interim measure, the NIC (Wohl, personal communication) has developed monthly mean ice-ocean masks, derived from their monthly mean climatology. These monthly masks exclude ice in areas that should be climatologically ice free. The masks will be applied to the data before they are used to initialize the PIPS2.0.

INITIALIZATION PROCESS

The SSM/I ice concentration is assimilated into the PIPS2.0 model in the following way. For the ice model section of the forecast system, the SSM/I data is used to totally replace the model's derived ice concentration. Then the ice thickness field is adjusted so that (a) ice is removed from those regions which are ice free in the SSM/I data and (b) ice is added to regions where the initialization data contains ice but the model does not. When ice is added to the thickness field, the amount of increase depends on

the ice concentration. If the ice concentration is between 15% and 50% and the ice thickness is less than 0.5 m, then the ice thickness is set to 0.3 m. If the area concentration is greater than 50% and the ice thickness is less than 0.5 m, then the ice thickness is increased to 0.6 m. For the ocean model section of the forecast system, the model is adjusted in the following way. In regions where ice has been added, the temperature of the first level of the ocean model is set to the freezing point, based on the salinity at that level. In regions where ice has been removed, the temperature of the first level is raised from the freezing point to 274.4° K to insure that ice does not immediately refreeze.

RESULTS

Figure 2 is an example of the PIPS2.0 ice concentration result for December 2, 1992 and can be compared to the SSM/I ice concentration data (Fig. 3) for the same day. The contours of all

Figure 2.
PIPS2.0 ice concentration (shown in percent) result for December 2, 1992. Contour interval is 10%.

Figure 3.
SSM/I ice concentration (shown in percent) for December 2, 1992. Contour interval is 10%.

the ice concentration plots begin at 20% and are incremented by 10% through 100%. The PIPS2.0 model was run without initialization from either the NIC or SSM/I ice concentration data. These results indicate that even without model initialization, the PIPS2.0 model has the capability to forecast seasonal trends. Figures 4 and 5 are examples of PIPS2.0 ice concentration results initialized with different frequencies. Figure 4 shows an example of PIPS2.0 being initialized on the first day (November 25, 1992) by SSM/I ice concentration data and run for 7 days. Figure 5 shows an example of PIPS2.0 being initialized every day, beginning on November 25, 1992, by SSM/I ice concentration data and run for 7 days. Both of these figures can be compared to the actual SSM/I image for the ending day (Fig. 3) and the result from PIPS2.0 without initialization (Fig. 2).

Figure 4.
PIPS2.0 ice concentration (shown in percent) result for a 7 day run ending on December 2, 1992. This result was initialized from a SSM/I image on November 25, 1992. Contour interval is 10%.

Figure 5.
PIPS2.0 ice concentration (shown in percent) result for a 7 day run ending on December 2, 1992.

This result was initialized on November 25, 1992 and updated daily with SSM/I ice concentration. Contour interval is 10%.

CONCLUSION

The Hibler ice model has been modified and adapted to a domain which includes most of the sea ice covered regions in the northern hemisphere. This model, coupled with the Cox ocean model, has been developed as an upgrade to the U.S. Navy's sea ice forecasting system, PIPS, and is called PIPS2.0. As the above figures show, although the model is capable of forecasting seasonal trends, some type of initialization is needed to keep the model's short term (days to weeks) forecasts accurate. At this point in time, each of the existing operational models are initialized once per week using the ice concentration from the NIC. Based on our tests, the forecasts should be greatly improved by using daily SSM/I data to initialize the PIPS2.0 system.

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